

The HuT

Networking activities

Deliverable D6.3

DEVELOPED WITHIN

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1. Technical references

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- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
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3. Introduction

The consortium is liaising with internationally recognized networks and other international projects dealing within aligned topics of interest for The HuT, with the aim of significantly expanding the boundaries of the consortium during the project and ensuring legacy of the project's innovations.

Networking activities are carried out employing different means:

- relationships with international networks engaged in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA);
- collaboration with other EU-funded projects and initiatives;
- participation to relevant events, such as meetings, conferences, training initiatives, clustering activities.

4. Relationships with international networks

The consortium has been purposefully structured to include: i) partners that have a leading role in relevant networks, and ii) a legacy advisory panel (LAP) comprising 5 representatives from internationally recognized networks dealing within aligned topics of interest for The HuT, who are invited to all consortium meetings.

The following networks have already liaised with The HuT:

- [GNDR](#), The Global Network of Civil Society Organisations for Disaster Reduction, an international network of over 1,400 member organisations across 127 countries, many of them grassroots and local community groups;
- [UCL Warning Research Center](#) and its network of over 40 warnings experts from all over the globe working with businesses, government, non-governmental, and intergovernmental organisations;
- [RiskKAN](#), the Risk-Knowledge Action Network on emergent risks and extreme events;
- [LandAware](#), the multi-disciplinary network fostering cooperation to address issues related to landslide early warning systems;
- [HIWeather](#), which is a World Meteorological Organisation World Weather Research Program activity focused on High Impact Weather;
- [Anticipation Hub](#), a network that brings together the Red Cross Red Crescent movement, universities, research institutes, NGO's and others involved in early action to reduce the impacts of hazards;
- [REAP](#), a Risk-informed Early Action Partnership launched by the UN at the Climate Action Summit in 2019 hosted by the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies.

5. Collaboration with other projects and initiatives

Collaborations and synergies with several ongoing European projects and initiatives have been initiated, to permit capitalizing the efforts among projects dealing with similar issues and minimizing the risk of duplicate work.

Fellow projects already in close contact with The HuT are reported in the following.

- **CORE**, sScience and human factOr for Resilient society
(Horizon 2020 project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101021746>)
A harmonised vision of crisis management awareness. Recent natural and man-made disasters in Europe have uncovered gaps in the level of preparedness. Increasing risk awareness is vital for disaster-resilient societies. The EU-funded CORE project will identify and implement best practice and knowledge, learning from seven past cases and from countries like Japan which has high levels of seismic and tsunami risk, but where risk awareness is high. Blending this European-specific and global best practice, CORE will provide optimised actions and harmonised solutions to rebuild socio-economic structures after a disaster. Through transdisciplinary collaboration involving environmental science and social science communities, it will define common metrics related to the different types of disasters, and how to measure, control and mitigate their impact.
- **MYRIAD-EU**, Multi-hazard and sYstemic framework for enhancing Risk-Informed mAnagement and Decision-making in the E.U.
(Horizon 2020 project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101003276>)
Forward-looking disaster risk management pathways. Protecting people, property, environment, and cultural heritage against disaster is a priority at the national and EU level. It is important for EU policymakers, decision-makers and practitioners across the Member States to come together to develop forward-looking disaster risk management pathways that assess trade-offs and synergies across sectors, hazards and scales. In this context, the EU-funded MYRIAD-EU project will inspire the introduction of a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk management. In addition to a web-based dashboard for navigating the framework, the project will also develop a laboratory of systemic multi-hazard risk assessment and management. The project will co-develop the framework with stakeholders in five multi-scale pilots: the North Sea, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, Danube and Veneto.
- **PARATUS**, Promoting disaster preparedness and resilience by co-developing stakeholder support tools for managing the systemic risk of compounding disasters
(Horizon Europe project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101073954>)
Innovative tools for disaster risk assessment. The ongoing pandemic and climate crisis have led disaster risk management stakeholders to consider adapting their risk reduction policies and emergency plans. However, there are no tools to assess the risks' cross-sectoral impacts. The EU-funded PARATUS project will develop an open-source platform for dynamic risk assessment to analyse and evaluate multi-hazard impact chains, risk reduction measures and disaster response scenarios under systemic vulnerabilities and uncertainties. The project will conduct forensic analysis on historical disaster events, supplement disaster databases with hazard interactions and sectoral impacts, and exploit remote sensing data with AI tools. The consortium includes research organisations, NGOs, SMEs, first-line responders and local and regional authorities.

- **DIRECTED**, Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing interoperable Data, models, communication and governance
(Horizon Europe project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101073978>)
Multi-hazard risk management through interoperability and co-creation. Extreme weather events are becoming more frequent and intense due to climate change. Efforts to enhance the disaster resilience of European societies is a top priority. In this context, the EU-funded DIRECTED project will foster communication, knowledge sharing and interoperability between different actors to help mitigate the impacts of extreme weather events. It will use a bottom-up, value-driven co-development approach to create new governance and risk management strategies. The establishment of a cloud platform called DATA-FABRIC will enable secure sharing of structured and unstructured data, while four Real World Labs will address topical problems of multi-hazard risk management and climate change adaptation. The overall goal of the project is to design and test new frameworks.
- **C2IMPRESS**, Co-creative improved understanding and awareness of multi-hazard risks for disaster resilient society
(Horizon Europe project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101074004>)
Making known the challenge of compound climate events and extremes. Compound weather and climate extremes involve a diverse set of events including concurrent climate extremes as well different non-standard high-impact events. One example is drought coupled with heat waves. These extreme weather and climate events can have devastating consequences. In this context, the EU-funded C2IMPRESS project will increase public awareness on multi-hazard risks. It will move the discussion away from the traditional 'hazard-centric' approach to a novel 'place and people'-centred integrated multi-hazard risk and resilient assessment framework. The project will develop several breakthrough innovations, such as a multi-hazard risk intelligence network platform supported by the robust Earth System Dynamic Intelligence and a suite of technologies to empower citizens and society with climate actions.
- **PEERS**, PracticE Ecosystem for standaRdS
(Horizon Europe project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101074040>)
A boost for preparedness and better practice in disasters. The pandemic, climate change, geopolitical conflicts, war and economic crises all highlight the need to protect citizens. The EU-funded PEERS project will enhance current policies regarding better practice in the European eco-system, through practitioner-driven pre-normative standardisation processes, which will be necessary for the safety and quality of life of workers throughout Europe. It will further support the improvement of preparedness and response in disaster risk reduction and chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear threats. This way, it will mobilise EU stakeholders and policymakers to improve European endurance and adaptability to future changes.
- **DISTENDER**, DevelopIng STRatEgies by integrating mitigation, aDaptation and participation to climate change Risks
(Horizon Europe project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056836>)
Responding to climate change risks and impacts with integrated strategies. Integrated strategies for climate change adaptation and mitigation involve efforts that simultaneously address the current and expected impacts and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The EU-funded DISTENDER project will create a methodological framework to respond to the impacts and risks of climate change. Using a participatory process, DISTENDER will develop multi-driver socio-economic climate scenarios that integrate bottom-up knowledge with top-down information. The project will also develop a cross-sectorial and multi-scale impact assessment modeling toolkit, as well as an economic evaluation framework to

assess the different efforts made. Five cases across a range of scales (city, regional, national and transnational) will test the DISTENDER holistic approaches, and six followers cases will be involved to support further replication of the methodology.

Since October 2023 The HuT has joined [CMINE](#), the Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe, and in particular the Societal Resilience Cluster of Projects (<https://www.cmine.eu/topics/20936/feed>). Under the scope of Horizon initiatives and other programmes funding policy relevant research in these issues, projects are associated into this "cluster" by virtue of their shared focus researching various aspects of Societal Resilience. This group is endorsed by both the Community for European Research and Innovation for Security (CERIS) and the European Research Executive Agency (REA), and holds regular meetings and other initiatives to which The HuT is actively contributing.

It is also worth noting that individual demonstrators within the HuT project are also forging their own relationships and collaborations with projects in Europe and globally. These relationships are being built from existing relationships or from the larger consortium collaborations with other projects and initiatives. This means that individual demonstrators can work directly with colleagues from these other projects on the areas of specific interest to their demonstrator to ensure the most value is gained from the collective knowledge of the global community (e.g., synergies have been established by the IIASA and UNIGE teams with the [Firelogue](#) and [Naturance](#) projects).

6. Participation to events

Many are the events to which The HuT partners have been participating to disseminate outcomes of project activities and to foster networking. Table 1 reports the main international dissemination/networking activities conducted to date.

Table 1: Main international dissemination/networking activities conducted to date (in reverse chronological order)

Name (period)	Type	Target audience	Short description
Participation in panel discussions (June 2024)	Clustering activities	Research communities; EU Institutions; Specific end user communities	Contribution to three panel discussions on different topics addressing the general theme "From Local to International Cooperation" at CERIS Disaster Resilient Societies Annual event, Bruxelles (Belgium)
Presentations at conference (June 2024)	Conferences	Research communities	Two presentations on multi-hazard warning systems at the 3rd International Conference on Natural Hazards and Risks in a Changing World, Amsterdam (Netherlands)
Presentations at EGU conference (April 2024)	Conferences	Research communities	Short course organized and project results presented in many different sessions of the European Geosciences Union (EGU) general assembly 2024, Vienna (Austria)
Participation in panel discussion (February 2024)	Clustering activities	EU Institutions; Specific end user communities	Panel discussion "Facing high impact low probability events disrupting our societies" organized by CERIS at international fair on Security, Madrid (Spain)
Participation in panel discussion (December 2023)	Clustering activities	Research communities; EU Institutions; Specific end user communities	Panel discussion "Towards an all-society approach to disaster resilience: from research to policy recommendations" at CERIS Disaster Resilient Societies Annual event, Bruxelles (Belgium)
Participation in panel discussion (September 2023)	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities; EU Institutions	Panel discussion at CORE project Stakeholders' Forum event "Improving collaboration and transfer from research to policy makers in the DRR context", Bruxelles (Belgium)
Participation in webinar (July 2023)	Education and training events	Industry, business partners; Specific end user communities; Local authorities; Regional authorities	Resilience Series Webinar "Crises in the making" organized by Cityforum

Organization of webinar (July 2023)	Education and training events	Specific end user communities; International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.); Civil society	Online webinar "Translating Warnings into Actions: Improving Early Warning Systems to Protect Communities"
Participation in policy seminar (June 2023)	Clustering activities	EU Institutions	Projects to Policy seminar organized by EU institutions in Bruxelles (Belgium)
Presentation in Conference (June 2023)	Conferences	Research communities; Specific end user communities	Conference "Climate crisis and systemic risks: Lessons Learned from COVID-19", Herrenhausen (Germany)
Organization of session in conference (June 2023)	Conferences	Research communities; Specific end user communities; Civil society	Science-art collaboration session "Staging Early Warning System stories" organized at the European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) in Dublin (Ireland)
Presentations at EGU conference (April 2023)	Conferences	Research communities	Project results presented in many different sessions of the European Geosciences Union (EGU) general assembly 2023, Vienna (Austria)
Participation in event (February 2023)	Education and training events	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Specific end user communities; Innovators	Co-creation lab on digitally-enabled approaches to sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics, organized by digiNEB.eu

